

ANALYSIS AND STUDY OF THE CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS OF ALLERGIC DISEASES IN CHILDREN BORN TO MOTHERS SUFFERING FROM ALLERGIC DISEASES

M.B. Devorova¹, M.J. Tursunboyeva², Sh.M. Yusupova³

PhD, Associate Professor of the Department of Family Doctor No. 1, Physical Education and
Civil Defense at Tashkent State Medical University^{1,2,3}

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17538787>

Abstract. *The article presents data from a literature review concerning the study of clinical manifestations of allergic diseases in children born to mothers suffering from allergic pathology. These aspects are of great importance for medical professionals, especially pediatricians. However, the investigation of this issue remains an open and pressing question.*

Keywords: *problem, children, pathology, prevalence, aspects.*

Introduction

Problems associated with allergic pathology in children have sharply increased over the past decades. According to statistical data, the number of children suffering from allergic diseases has more than doubled in the last five years. Research findings indicate that 40% of the affected population are young children: 54% of them suffer from atopic dermatitis, and in 10% of cases, the first symptoms of bronchial asthma appear during the first year of life. Modern genetic analyses have shown that about 70% of children who develop allergic pathology at an early age have a family history burdened by similar diseases. The degree of risk is determined by the nature of inheritance and environmental factors, including the course of delivery, type of feeding, living conditions, and parents' harmful habits.

According to literature data, it is well known that allergic inflammation is based on adrenergic receptor dysfunction and hyperproduction of IgE by immunocompetent cells. The study of adrenoceptor disorders in recent years has led to the development of a concept of generalized beta-adrenoceptor pathology, which affects all cells and tissues of the body. Essentially, this is regarded as a manifestation of ontogenetic immaturity of the membrane-receptor structures of body cells. Genetic studies have identified associations between certain variants of the β_2 -adrenoceptor gene and allergic diseases. An information review revealed that, despite the relatively well-studied sensitivity of beta-adrenoceptors in adults suffering from allergic disorders, questions regarding the condition of beta-adrenoceptors in newborns and young children with a hereditary predisposition to allergic pathology remain insufficiently explored. Moreover, there are no data on the impact of maternal chronic diseases on the development of adrenoceptor dysfunction in newborns.

Until recently, one of the generally accepted methods for predicting allergic diseases in newborns was the determination of eosinophil count and IgE levels in umbilical cord blood. However, recent studies have demonstrated that these laboratory indicators cannot be considered reliable markers of the mentioned risk. Epidemiological studies of recent years confirm a high prevalence of bronchial asthma (BA) among both children and adults, averaging from 5% to 10%.

Bronchial asthma belongs to the group of multifactorial diseases (MFDs), the etiology and pathogenesis of which are determined by a complex interaction of genetic and environmental factors.

In the manifestation of genetically determined defects, external influences on the mother's and child's bodies play a significant role — such as unbalanced nutrition, high antigenic load, respiratory infections, and other causes. The beginning of the 21st century has been marked by an alarming increase in the number of patients with various allergic diseases, among which bronchial asthma ranks first. The main cause of this increase is considered to be the growing antigenic load on the human body in the era of environmental aggression and westernization of lifestyle.

According to domestic researchers, for example, in St. Petersburg, about 20% of the population suffers from allergic diseases, including 7.3% with bronchial asthma. It should also be noted that the severity of allergic diseases, particularly bronchial asthma, is increasing worldwide. This is largely due to late diagnosis, which leads to delayed initiation of treatment.

The presented facts lead to the conclusion that it is necessary to search for new ways to prevent the development of allergic diseases, particularly bronchial asthma (BA). According to the literature, bronchial asthma is a serious chronic disease that poses a significant public health problem. This disease has a hereditary predisposition. The realization of genetically determined defects is influenced by adverse environmental and occupational factors affecting the mother and fetus, unbalanced nutrition, high allergen exposure in the child's body, respiratory infections, and other causes. The higher the degree of predisposition to allergy, the less external exposure is required for the disease to manifest. Under strong exposure to a combination of allergenic factors, even children with a minor predisposition may develop allergic diseases.

Bronchial asthma is not a contraindication to pregnancy, but poorly controlled disease during this period adversely affects the health of both the mother and the unborn child. Epidemiological studies among pregnant women have shown that bronchial asthma is quite common in this group — according to various authors, from 1% to 13.8% of pregnant women suffer from this disease. Specialists have established that the severity structure of the disease in pregnant women approximately corresponds to that of bronchial asthma in general, i.e., patients with mild forms predominate (65–70%).

Earlier studies indicated an approximately equal number of patients reporting improvement, worsening, or stable course of bronchial asthma during pregnancy. However, recent data demonstrate a tendency toward an increased number of cases with exacerbation of the disease. Research conducted in recent years has shown that placental insufficiency and fetal growth retardation were more often observed in women who did not receive treatment for bronchial asthma. At the same time, patients with controlled disease successfully carried pregnancies to term and gave birth to healthy children when timely basic therapy was prescribed. At present, there is no established system that allows for primary prevention of allergic diseases — particularly bronchial asthma — in children born to mothers suffering from this condition.

The authors have confirmed that, in most cases, allergy represents the initial sensitization, against which hypersensitivity to other types of allergens develops, leading to various chronic allergic and gastroenterological pathologies. Moreover, the spectrum of intolerable foods changes with age: while the initial sensitization is most often caused by cow's milk proteins (CMP), in older children, allergies to foods such as fish, honey, nuts, citrus fruits, and others become more common. In infants during their first year of life who are on artificial or mixed feeding, the success of dietary therapy largely depends on the correct selection of a breast milk substitute. To optimally

solve this problem, it is necessary to develop a modern, differentiated, and scientifically grounded approach.

An additional challenge is the correction of the nutrient composition of the diet in older children and adolescents suffering from long-term allergies and having restricted diets that exclude nutritionally important foods. It should be noted that the duration of elimination diets is not clearly defined at present. In this regard, it is necessary to clarify the clinical and immunological criteria that determine the duration of elimination of various foods and the timing of their reintroduction into the child's diet during nutritional expansion, as well as to develop approaches for dietary correction in patients on long-term elimination diets using modern nutraceuticals.

Experts have also confirmed another important factor: the oral route of allergen exposure leads to the development of various gastrointestinal disorders in most patients with allergies. The nature of these disorders varies depending on the child's age and the severity of sensitization. The role of non-IgE-mediated mechanisms in the formation of gastrointestinal manifestations of allergy is not yet fully understood and requires further investigation. In recent years, there has been active research into the influence of intestinal microflora on the development of the immune system. Various disturbances in the composition of the intestinal microbiota are frequently observed in children suffering from food allergies. Studies have shown that the intestinal microflora of healthy children differs from that of children with atopy — atopic children have a reduced number of lactobacilli and an increased number of coliform bacteria and *Staphylococcus aureus*.

When profound alterations occur in the intestinal biocenosis—characterized by suppression of protective microflora and active proliferation of conditionally pathogenic microorganisms—these changes affect the course of the allergic process, contributing to its aggravation. However, the pathogenetic significance of intestinal microbiota disturbances in allergic children has not been fully elucidated. Clinicians note that dietary therapy is a key component of comprehensive allergy treatment, being essentially an etiotropic method of therapy. When developing a therapeutic diet, primary attention is given to the elimination of causative foods. At the same time, regardless of the stage of the disease, the diet must meet the physiological needs of children for essential nutrients, vitamins, and minerals. Therapeutic nutrition for allergies has its own specific features at different ages. Thus, summarizing the literature review, it can be concluded that further research in this area of medicine is of significant value.

A positive family history of allergic pathology is considered one of the most significant risk factors for the development of these diseases in children. The presence of bronchial asthma in parents significantly increases the risk of the disease in offspring. When comparing parental lines, the maternal history of asthma has a more pronounced effect than the paternal one, which confirms the importance of intrauterine factors in the formation of allergy and bronchial asthma in particular.

Further analysis of literature sources has shown that in studies devoted to the course of pregnancy in women with bronchial asthma, the health status of the child was found to depend on the severity and controllability of the mother's disease during pregnancy. However, only a few studies have presented long-term follow-up data on children born to mothers with bronchial asthma. Practically no studies have investigated the influence of the clinical and pathogenetic features of maternal bronchial asthma on the formation of allergic pathology in the child. In addition, there are very limited data on the interaction of genes involved in the genetic network of bronchial asthma and their influence on the development of the allergic status of children born to mothers with this disease.

Conclusion. Thus, a review of the literature allows us to conclude that it is relevant and necessary to study the genotypic and phenotypic characteristics of children born to mothers suffering from bronchial asthma, as well as to identify their risk of developing allergic pathology through dynamic observation. Knowledge of the unfavorable genetic profile at birth will make it possible to identify high-risk groups for the development of this pathology, and expanding our understanding of the factors influencing allergic disease formation in children will help develop methods for early prevention of these disorders.

REFERENCES

1. Irsha Herr Doktor der historischen Wissenschaften. (Bratislava, Slowakei)
2. Khoroshkevych A. L. Doktor der historischen Wissenschaften (Moskau, Russland)
3. Ermolenko C. Doktor der philologischen Wissenschaften (Kiew. Ukraine)
4. In Качкан. Doktor der philologischen Wissenschaften (Iwano-Frankiwsk, Ukraine)
5. Devorova M.B. Allergic diseases in children. World Bulletin of Public Health (WBPH) Журналы Scholar Express. Берлин, Германия. Volume-31, February 2024. С.111-113.
6. Smith P.K., Collins J. Carney A.S. International Consensus Statement on Allergy and Rhinology: Allergic Rhinitis//Int Forum Allergy Rhinol.2023;13(Suppl 1):S1-S70.
7. Devorova M.B., Koshimbetova G.K Influence of allergic recurrent obstructive bronchitis on physical development of preschool children International Virtual Conference on Language and Literature Proceeding. Part .4 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10113496> Indonesia January June 2024-2. С. 34-35;
8. Devorova M.B. Current aspects of treatment and complications of covid in children with allergic diseases (literary review) World Bulletin of Public Health .Журналы Scholar Express. Available Online at: <https://www.scholarexpress.net> Берлин, Германия Volume-22, May 2023. С.33-36;
9. Shvets N.G., Doktor der Wirtschaftswissenschaften, Professor;
10. Bocharov V. A., der Doktor der medizinischen Wissenschaften, Professor, der Odessa Medical Institute des Internationalen humanitären Universität;
11. Waldemar Wójcik, Doktor der technischen Wissenschaften, Professor, Lubliner öko-University of Technology;
12. Weber A. I., Doktor der politischen Wissenschaften, Professor der Kiewer nationalen Taras-Sche-wtschenko-Universität;